

"Life" is an Effect, Not the Cause:

The Coordination of Matter and Energy as a Fundamental Principle of Functional Systems

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Summary

This essay explores the idea that the coordination of matter and energy is the underlying principle of all functional systems, living or non-living, serving as the basis for any observable organization. The cell, as the fundamental unit of living systems, is highlighted as the clearest example of this universal principle. It is argued that the cell, being essentially matter and energy in autonomous coordination, exemplifies how functionality emerges from this coordination. "Life," in its complexity, is an emergent effect of this self-generated and autonomous coordination of matter and energy, which precedes and makes possible any functionality. Recognizing the cell as a manifestation of this universal principle transcends the distinction between life and non-life, offering a unifying approach to understanding natural systems.

Keywords: Matter and Energy Coordination; Functional Systems; Cell; Life; Autopoiesis; Self; Coordinated Energy; Thermodynamics; Open Systems; Entropy; Intricacy; Organization; Cellular Autonomy; Universal Principle; ATP parity; Matter and Energy; Internal Order; Living Systems; Non-Living Systems; Self.

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Introduction

The distinction between living and non-living systems has been central to science and philosophy. However, when considering that the coordination of matter and energy is the basis of all functionality, this distinction loses importance. This essay proposes that **life, including its most fundamental systems such as the cell, is a particular and observable manifestation of a universal principle: the autonomous, self-generated coordination of matter and energy.**

By highlighting the cell as an example of this principle, it is possible to connect biological and physical concepts, promoting an integrated view of natural phenomena. Furthermore, by focusing on the fact that the cell is nothing more than matter and energy in autonomous coordination, we reinforce the idea that "life" is an emergent effect of this fundamental coordination.

Coordinated Matter/Energy is Universal and Essential

The coordination of matter and energy is observable in systems of all scales, from atoms to galaxies. Prigogine (1977) demonstrated that systems far from thermodynamic equilibrium can develop order through dissipative processes, showing that coordination is fundamental for the emergence of organized structures. Bertalanffy (1968), in *the General Theory of Systems*, highlighted that organizational principles transcend categories such as living and non-living, reinforcing that coordination is the essence of functionality.

The cell, as a self-sustaining system, is a concrete example of how the coordination of matter and energy enables functionality. Through highly regulated processes such as ATP production, molecule transport, and cell division, the cell demonstrates that coordination is not unique to life, but its essential basis.

The Cell: Matter and Energy in Autonomous Coordination

The cell is, in its essence, an organization of matter and energy. It is not something beyond or separate from these fundamental components; It is a direct manifestation of the intrinsic coordination of matter and energy. The molecules that make up the cell—proteins, lipids, carbohydrates, and nucleic acids—are organized forms of matter. The processes that occur within the cell, such as chemical reactions and ionic flows, are transformations and transfers of energy.

This internal coordination allows the cell to maintain its structure and function as a coherent system. There is no external agent directing these functions; they emerge from the inherent properties of the material and energy components of the cell. Thus, the cell exemplifies the universal logic that functional systems are the result of the autonomous, self-generated coordination of matter and energy.

ATP Parity: Fundamental Matter/Energy Balance

ATP (adenosine triphosphate) is the cell's main energy currency, acting as an intermediary between processes that release and consume energy. **ATP parity** refers to the instantaneous and continuous balance between its production and consumption. This balance is critical because the cell does not store ATP in large quantities; it depends on constant production that exactly corresponds to immediate energy demands.

Any disruption in this balance results in failure in the coordination of matter and energy. If ATP production does not keep up with its consumption, essential cellular processes cease, quickly leading to loss of cellular integrity. The cell then returns to a state of uncoordinated matter and energy, highlighting that its existence as a functional system depends entirely on this balance.

This parity is not maintained by an external force, but rather by the cell's own internal mechanisms. Enzymes and metabolic pathways continuously adjust the rates of ATP production and consumption in response to energy needs, exemplifying the self-generated and autonomous coordination of matter and energy.

Autopoiesis and Autonomy

The concept of autopoiesis (Maturana and Varela 1980) describes the cell as a system capable of self-generation and self-sustaining. The cell organizes matter and energy to produce components that keep it functional, validating the idea that life emerges from autonomous coordination. This self-generated and autonomous ability to maintain internal order is a direct manifestation of the universal principle of matter and energy coordination.

"Life" is an Effect, Not the Cause

Life, as perceived in cellular systems, is an emergent effect of the coordination of matter and energy. Kauffman (1993) pointed out that complex systems, under certain conditions, naturally self-organize, leading to the emergence of properties such as self-regulation and reproduction. Schrödinger (1944) pointed out that life maintains its internal order by exporting entropy to the environment. This maintenance of order is only possible through efficient energy coordination, as exemplified by the cell.

Therefore, life is not the cause of coordination, but rather a result of it. **The cell, being essentially matter and energy in autonomous coordination, exemplifies how functionality emerges from this coordination.** By recognizing that the coordination of matter and energy is the basis of everything, "life" ceases to be an exclusive attribute and becomes a particular manifestation of this universal principle.

Matter and Energy Coordination Precedes Any Functionality

Energy coordination is the basis of any functional system, living or not. Morowitz (1968) argued that the flow of energy is crucial to the emergence of organization. In the case of the cell, energy coordination is essential for the production of biomolecules and for the maintenance of metabolic processes.

The parity between ATP production and consumption, as a central manifestation of this coordination, exemplifies how coordinated energy precedes and sustains functionality. Without this parity, any cell — and, by extension, any functional system — becomes unviable. This reinforces the idea that self-generated and autonomous coordination of matter and energy is a prerequisite for functionality.

Discussion

The realization that the cell is a universal manifestation of the coordination of matter and energy redefines the distinction between life and non-life. Cellular functionality, including processes such as division and intercellular communication, can be understood as a direct effect of this coordination.

By considering the cell from this perspective, we advance in the understanding of biological and physical systems as expressions of the same unifying principle. Open systems thermodynamics, as described by Prigogine (1977), offers insights into how systems such as the cell maintain their internal order when interacting with the environment.

Recognizing that **the cell is essentially matter and energy in autonomous coordination** allows for a more integrated and comprehensive analysis of natural

phenomena. This unifying perspective promotes the idea that coordination ceases to be an exclusive attribute of "life" and becomes an all-encompassing and universal concept.

Conclusion

The self-generated and autonomous coordination of matter and energy is the fundamental principle that underpins all functional systems. **The cell, being nothing more than matter and energy in autonomous coordination, exemplifies this universal principle.** "Life," in its complexity, is an emergent effect of this coordination, not its cause.

By transcending the traditional distinctions between life and non-life, we can unify the analysis of natural systems under a single logic. The cell, in its functionality and self-regulation, offers the clearest example of how the coordination of matter and energy precedes and enables functionality.

This integrated view has the potential to broaden our understanding of complex systems and promote advances in several areas, from cell biology to physics and materials sciences. **Recognizing coordination as the fundamental principle opens avenues for new research and a more unifying approach in science.**

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